

E-PLACEMENT TRAINING CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT: A DRAFT

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Abstract :

Conducting professional training of placement assistance seeking students at campus is one of the foremost aims for a Training & Placement Department in an Institution. Considering the nature of skillsets demanded in today's technology driven job/employment markets as well as at E-HRM powered online e-campus interview processes for students, the need for possessing a fully-fledged comprehensive training plan at institution side is becoming far more essential. Therefore, with a view to device a solution for meeting this training need, an honest attempt is made here in this study to draft a robust training syllabus covering all aspects of industry expectations. The industry expectations in the e-placement training draft related to student skill procurement through the concepts of Online or E-Recruiting as an intended outcome is explored. Also, an implementation methodology or guide to institutions in devising the developed curriculum in their pedagogy is also determined to be thought here in this research paper.

Keywords : E-Placement Training, Online Placement Coaching, Training Plan, E-Campus Placement, E-Campus Recruitment

I. Introduction

Present days in industry recruitment or selection processes is the foreplay of E-HRM in the limelight. E-HRM refers to widespread usage & application of electronic methodologies, digital platforms plus cutting-edge technologies plus world wide web internet to social media in candidate recruitment process. E-HRM is significantly influencing campus recruitment processes at business schools presently and is expected to be recognized as a standard single running procedure or format to be followed in future by campus recruiters with rapid

development in Automation, Robotics, Artificial Intelligence Technology as well as Internet of Things (IoT) or any other revolutions in digital world. This E-HRM powered process is identified as online e-campus interview/placement/recruitment at management institutions. Apparently, Industry in this regard is expecting the Training & Placement teams at business schools to train the students to confront or interface E-HRM process powered online e-campus interviews in the days coming to upskill the campus student talent pool for their career prospects in Industry. Amidst their profit pursuit, not all Industries have found out time to roll out any hands-on E-HRM training manuals, framework/processes or rather their own complete front to end online e-interview job application guides to business schools for incorporating the same in institute's employment training initiatives. (Industry-Academia Gap). There is no particular or certified syllabus found in academic semester pedagogy as subject or even as a separate certificate program in Degree/PG courses pertaining to "Online E-Placement Training & Development" towards fostering confidence in "Vocational Skills" among young placement aspiring business management graduates. Currently, institutions are shelling exorbitant payments to outsourced external training agencies (middlemen in industry-academia gap) towards interview training. The Placement Cell is arranging these expensive training dealing with these agencies. Therefore, this study aims to solve the above dilemma by proposing a draft online e-campus interview facing syllabus to effectively train the job seeking graduates in educational institution campuses.

II. Objectives of the Paper :

The primary objective of this paper is to construct a draft 'e-campus interview preparation *training* syllabus' to be taught as a curriculum in higher educational institutions. The study aims to be a partner in development of effective employability curriculum towards student centred applications in higher education [1]

III. Research Methodology

For developing the syllabus and teaching plan, A Training requirement assessment was undertaken based on Box Framework of campus interview training propounded by Shenoy & Aithal (2017) [2]. Additionally, Scholarly literature review, Data collection from Industry sources, and Focus Group interview with expert panels were undertaken for structuring the components of curriculum. The developed Syllabus is displayed in academic method

IV. About BOX Framework of E-Campus Interview Training :

The proposed BOX framework or Four Box Model of e-campus interview training above is a very simple and highly useful validated approach for designing online interview skills-oriented e-training models propounded by Shenoy & Aithal (2017). As shown in the constructs, almost all of the training constituents which have been suggested in the diagram can easily be classified within the framework under its primary focus areas consisting each deployment modules. This Model was mainly developed to meet the requirements of E-HRM functions of the present-day technology driven employment market and recruiters for hiring student freshers from educational institution campuses. Just like how analysis of employee training

needs in Information Technology Industry, Knowledge and Skill levels required for employees are assessed, BOX Framework functions to device suitable training programs with appropriate contents for Virtual Campus Interviews [3-4-5]

V. Proposed Draft Syllabus for E-Placement Interview Training :

Semester 1

UNIT 1 : Soft Skills Training for virtual electronic processes

Introduction, professional behaviour and gratitude in virtual platforms, Posture Display during interaction using electronic communication forms, E-Mail, Chats, Blogs and Website communications.

UNIT 2 : Introduction to ICT Devices, Audio-Visual Medium, and Electronic Communication

Meaning and Significance of ICT (Information & Communications Technology), Audio-Visual Medium, and Electronic Communication, ICT Handling exposure and Simulation practice training, Interactive Voice Response (IVR).

UNIT 3 : Online Profiling

Understanding Social Media as a tool for profile branding, Building Social Media Profiles, Online Image Management.

UNIT 4 : Personality Development and CV/Resume Building

Significance of Cover Letter and CV/Resume, Necessary elements of CV/Resume, Sending Online Job Applications and resume uploads, Various Resume Building Mechanisms.

Semester 2

UNIT 1 : Online Aptitude Test

Introduction to Online Aptitude Test, Understanding General Aptitude and Domain Aptitude, Reasoning and Data Sufficiency, General and Business Awareness.

UNIT 2 : Online Video-Conferencing

Understanding Webinars, Online Panel Interviews, Knowing the art of video-conferencing, various video conferencing tools.

UNIT 3 : Online Registrations and Form Fillings

Art of filling web forms for job applications, Important things to remember while filling job application or interview opportunity forms online as registrations

UNIT 4 : Online Mock Interview

Preparing Tips for E-Interviews, Online Interview Simulations, Coaching for deviations

Semester 3

UNIT 1 : Undertaking Telephonic Interviews

Understanding Smart Phones as devices or platforms of Interview, Necessary telephonic etiquettes candidates must know, further do's and don'ts in telephonic conversations

UNIT 2 : Practising with bots for influence

Interacting with Instant Messengers (IM), Knowing Chat Bots and Internet Relay Chats (IRC) related to employment or online HR Forums of companies.

UNIT 3 : Online or E-Group Discussions

Etiquettes of e-group discussions, do's and don'ts in video forums, focus and concentration building

UNIT 4 : Targeting companies online for job application

Knowing various job search websites, search engines, online job boards and blogs, following-up the leads and referral, developing professional online networks.

Semester 4

UNIT 1 : Determining Placement Quotient (PQ)

IEDRA Model of Student Job Placement Realization [6], Developing a Placement Quotient for interview facing confidence.

UNIT 2 : Employability Skill Chart for online interviews

E-Communication Skills, Online Skill based course certifications, Basic Technical Knowledge of Hardware and Software Applications

UNIT 3 : Career Counselling in Online Environment

Understanding Career Therapy in digital work environments, Creating and Building Career Motivation in technology environments, Seeking Career Support and guidance E-HRM Space.

UNIT 4 : Final E-Campus Interview Preparations

Various Technological tools required for giving the interviews, Other necessary checklists and skillsets to be verified before the interview.

IV. Analysis, Interpretation & Findings :

The above discussed curriculum is perceived to saves cost to institutions on employing, investing or depending on expensive external trainers for contents. Basing on revenue model, Institution can offer this syllabus as optional/choice-based OR even as mandatory subject as part of semesters or perhaps as a separate vocational skill development certificate course for aspiring students. The Training & Placement Cell hereby also becomes a partner along with other department in offering subject thereby leading to optimum utilization of departments for institution management. The pedagogical implications of student learning from above curriculum for online interviews could be further determined as learning in virtual campus is practised in institutions [7-8]. The Benefit of additional career services available in this format for job seeking graduate students in campus can also include an internal assessment consisting of interview skill building activity providing a virtual interview to develop interviewing skills as well as placement and recruiting and mentor matching [9].

V. Conclusion

The scope of the present study is limited to 2 years Post-Graduation academic study durations only. We have not considered 3 Years Graduation or 4 Years academic study duration expecting to be a part of future research studies and replicate on other courses to make it towards a more generalized model in near future. Furthermore, the detailed study of the graduate student skills and the necessary skills required to clear the online campus interviews at entry levels are only done. A Supporting draft paper on “Session-wise Training Topic Plan for Online E-Campus Interviews” for training or teaching above e-campus interview facing syllabus is expected to commence shortly as a follow-up to this study.

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